
pcDNA5/FRT-EGFR-HA-TEV-Halo

 pcDNA5FRT-Halo-AsiSI-PmeI-pcDNA5Rev_D10.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-Halo-AsiSI-PmeI-CMV-F_C10.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-c-HA-Halo_2-pcDNA-Rev_C10.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-c-HA-Halo_5-pcDNA-Rev_D10.ab1

 pcDNA5-c-HA-Halo_5-CMV-Fwd_H01.ab1

 pcDNA5-c-HA-Halo_5-P7_G01.ab1

 pcDNA5-c-HA-Halo_5-CMV-Fwd_H01.ab1

 pcDNA5-c-HA-Halo_5-P7_G01.ab1

 pcDNA5FRT-CD44-HA-Halo_B4-Halo-Rev.seq

 pcDNA5FRT-CD44-HA-Halo_B5-Halo-Rev.seq

 pcDNA5FRT-MECOM-HA-Halo_H3-MECOM_F1.seq

 pcDNA5FRT-MECOM-HA-Halo_H3-MECOM_F2.seq

 pcDNA5FRT-MECOM-HA-Halo_H3-MECOM_F3.seq

 pcDNA5FRT-MECOM-HA-Halo_H3-MECOM_F4.seq

 pcDNA5FRT-MECOM-HA-Halo_H3-MECOM_F5.seq

 pcDNA5FRT-MECOM-HA-Halo_H3-MECOM_F6.seq

 pcDNA5FRT-MECOM-HA-Halo_H3-CMV-Fwd.seq

 pcDNA5FRT-MECOM-HA-Halo_H3-Halo-seq-Rev.seq

 pcDNA5-CD166-HA-Halo_F4-CD166-F1.seq

 pcDNA5-CD166-HA-Halo_F4-CD166-F2.seq

 pcDNA5-CD166-HA-Halo_F4-CD166-F3.seq

 pcDNA5FRT-CD166-HA-Halo_F4-CMV-seq-Fwd.seq

 pcDNA5FRT-CD166-HA-Halo_F4-Halo-seq-Rev.seq

 pcDNA5FRT-EGFR-HA-Halo_G2-CMV-Fwd.seq

 pcDNA5FRT-EGFR-HA-Halo_G2-Halo-seq-Rev.seq

 pcDNA5FRT-EGFR-HA-Halo_G2-EGFR_F1.seq

 pcDNA5FRT-EGFR-HA-Halo_G2-EGFR_F2.seq

 pcDNA5FRT-EGFR-HA-Halo_G2-EGFR_F3.seq

 pcDNA5FRT-EGFR-HA-Halo_G2-EGFR_F4.seq

 pcDNA5FRT-EGFR-HA-Halo_G2-EGFR_F5.seq

 pcDNA5FRT-EGFR-HA-Halo_G2-EGFR_F6.seq